

A new sensitive method for the determination of deltamethrine in environmental, agricultural and biological samples

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Abstract : A new sensitive method for the determination of deltamethrine pesticide in ppm level is described. The method is based on the hydrolysis of deltamethrine to produce cyanide ion which reacts with bromine water to form cyanogen bromide. To this solution on adding potassium iodide solution to remove excess of bromine which react with Leuco Crystal Violet. The formation of dye has maximum absorbance 590 nm and Beer's law is obeyed in the range of 0.4–2.6 ppm. The molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity, correlation coefficient have been determined. The method is highly reproducible and have been successfully applied to the determination of deltamethrine pesticides in environmental agricultural and biological samples.

Keywords : Deltamethrine, pesticide.

Deltamethrine insecticide is used to control a number of insect species on economic crops. Deltamethrine is effective pest control chemical and have low mammalian toxicity¹. The objective of the proposed work is to develop a rapid, low cost, accurate and simple analytical methods for the determination of deltamethrine at trace levels. In this paper, a simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method is described for the determination of deltamethrine where deltamethrine is hydrolysed in alkaline medium to give cyanide ion and then adding the bromine water to form cyanogen bromide which further react with potassium iodide and leuco crystal violet to produce a crystal violet dye with maximum absorbance at 590 nm. The reagent is selective for deltamethrine, amongst the pyrethroid group. The colour system obeys Beer's law in the range of 0.4–2.6 ppm of deltamethrine. The method has been applied to the determination of deltamethrine in various samples of water, vegetables, fruits, foliages and biological samples.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents : A Systronics UV-Vis spectrophotometric model 104 with matched silical cells was used for all spectral measurements. A Systronic pH meter model 335 was used for pH measurements. A Remi C-854/4 clinical centrifuge force of 1850 g with fixed swing out rotors was used for centrifugation.

All reagents used were of AnalaR grade or of the best available quality. Double distilled demineralized water was used throughout.

Deltamethrine (Syngenta Crop Protection Private Limited, India) : A stock solution of 1 mg mL⁻¹ was prepared in ethanol. Working standard solutions were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock standard solution with water.

Bromine water : Saturated Bromine Water was used.

Sodium hydroxide : 20% aqueous solution was used.

Potassium iodide : 0.1% aqueous solution was used.

Leuco crystal violet (Eastman Kodak Co.) [LCV] : To a 1 liter volumetric flask 200 ml of water, 3 ml of 85% phosphoric acid and 250 mg of leuco crystal i.e. 4,4',4''-methylidynetris (*N,N'*-dimethylaniline) (CH[C₆H₄N(CH₃)₂]₃) were added and shaken gently until the dye gets dissolved. The content of the flask was then diluted to 1 liter with water.

An aliquot of test solution containing of deltamethrine was taken in a 25 mL graduated tube and to it, 1.0 ml of 20% sodium hydroxide was added. The solution was kept for 10 min at room temperature for complete hydrolysis. Then 1 mL of 0.1% potassium iodide was added in acidic medium, to liberate iodine and then 1 mL leuco crystal violet was added and shaken thoroughly and kept for 15

min for full colour development. The crystal violet dye was produced. The solution was then diluted to the mark with water and absorbance was measured at 590 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and discussion

Spectral characteristics : The crystal violet dye formed in the proposed reaction shows maximum absorption at 590 nm. All spectral measurements were carried out against demineralized water as the reagent blank showed negligible absorption at this wavelength. The colour system obeys Beer's law in the range of 0.4 to 2.6 μg of deltamethrine per 25 mL of final solution at 590 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $3.3 \times 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.054 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

Hydrolysis of deltamethrine to cyanide ion was studied at different temperatures and alkalinity. It was observed that alkaline conditions were required for the hydrolysis. Maximum hydrolysis was observed with 20% sodium hydroxide at temperature range of 30–35 °C as it gave maximum absorbance values, good stability and quantitative results. It was observed that 1 mL of leuco crystal violet was sufficient for complete colour reaction.

The effect of pH on the colour reaction was studied and it was found that constant absorbance values were obtained at pH range of 8.4–9.1 by sodium hydroxide and no buffer solution was required to stabilize the colour. The coloured species remain stable for more than 7 days under optimum conditions.

Precision of the method was checked by the replicate analysis of working standard solution containing 4 μg of

deltamethrine in 25 ml final solution over a period of 7 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.002 and 21% respectively.

The effect of common foreign species and pesticides were studied to assess the validity of the method. Known amounts of foreign species and pesticides were added to the standard solution contained 10 μg of deltamethrine prior to hydrolysis and the solution was analysed by the proposed method. The method was found to be free from interferences of most of the foreign species and pesticides. Tolerance limit range : around 100 ppm for organic solvents; 40–100 ppm for different metal ions and lower values for anionic radicals.

Application : Various samples of vegetables, fruits and foliage each of 25 g, were taken, collected from agricultural field, where deltamethrine had been sprayed as an insecticide. The samples were macerated with two 20 mL portions of ethanol-demineralized water (1+1), filtered through a thin cotton cloth and filtrate was centrifuged at 1850 g for 10 min. In case of vegetables and fruits the filtrate was quantitatively transferred into a 50 mL calibrated flask and made up to the mark with 50% ethanol. Aliquots of supernatant were taken in a 25 mL graduated tube and to it, 1.0 mL of 20% sodium hydroxide was added and kept for 10 min at room temperature for complete hydrolysis. Then 1 mL of potassium iodide and leuco crystal violet was added and kept for 15 min for full colour development. The solution was then diluted to the mark with water and absorbance was measured at 595 nm against a reagent blank.

In case of foliage, the filtrate was passed through a silica gel column (10 \times 1 cm) filled with 5 g silica gel,

Table 1. Determination of deltamethrine in environmental and agricultural samples

Samples	Deltamethrine originally found ^a (μg)	Deltamethrine added (μg)	Total deltamethrine (found)	Difference (c - a)	Recovery (%)
	(a)	(b)	(c)		$\frac{(c - a)}{b} \times 100$
Water ^b	1.25	10	11.11	9.86	98.6
	3.42	20	23.32	19.9	99.5
Tomato ^c	2.37	10	12.28	9.91	99.1
	4.13	20	23.97	19.87	99.2
Apple ^c	1.87	10	10.75	8.88	88.8
	4.22	20	22.12	17.9	89.5
Cauliflower ^c	4.11	10	13.89	9.78	97.8
	5.29	20	25.07	19.78	98.9

^aMean of three replicate analyses.

^bWater sample 25 mL, 1 mL aliquot of sample was analyzed, after treatment as described in procedure.

^cSample 25 g (sample taken from a field where deltamethrine had been sprayed).

which was found to be sufficient for removal of chlorophyll and other interfering materials present in the extracted sample². The column was washed with 10 ml of 50% ethanol, washings were collected in a 25 mL calibrated flask and aliquots were analysed as recommended above (Table 1).

River water samples, which received run off water from agricultural field, were collected. These samples were filtered through a Whatman No. 40 filter paper. Aliquots of water samples were taken in a 25 mL graduated tube, to it sodium hydroxide was added and analysed as described above (Table 1).

Recovery of deltamethrine in biological samples : Since the presence of deltamethrine in blood and urine has been reported in detectable concentration³. The method has been applied for the determination of deltamethrine in biological samples. Synthetic samples were prepared by adding known amounts of deltamethrine to these samples and then analysed after deproteination with trichloroacetic acid as described above⁴. Recovery percentage in blood is $\sim 95 \pm 2$ and in urine it is 85 ± 3 .

Conclusion :

The proposed method is rapid, simple and sensitive and reagent described here is sensitive and selective for deltamethrine insecticides containing a nitrile group.

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